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Career Choice of Girl Child in Contemporary India Suruchi Bhatia* and Nandita Babu**

Abstract

The current paper attempts to outline the pervasive cultural beliefs that contribute to gender socialization of women's career-choices in India. Cultural beliefs along with actual ability influence an individual's perceptions of its competence at various career-relevant tasks. To the extent that individuals then act on gender-differentiated perceptions when making career decisions, cultural beliefs about gender channel men and women in substantially different career directions. For the purpose of developing a coherent perspective, articles from both eastern and western perspective were included. A careful review of existing literature suggests the role of internalization of gender stereotypes on the part of women in shaping their explicit and implicit career preferences. Furthermore, an outline of the trajectory of career choices of women indicates factors like parenting, maintenance of work-life balance, and familial obligations to transform and contribute to their career-decision making. Based on the review, this article recommends (a) the development of more robust theoretical perspectives that better suit the eastern cultures, and (b) a reconceptualization of "career counselling" to include a holistic understanding of the factors that contribute to (or alternatively hinder) the career or vocational choices made by girls.

Keywords: career decision-making, academic gender segregation, career counselling, parenting, empowering women.

In India there are times, when women are treated as Goddesses and their feet are touched for blessings, and then there are also times when they have to hide themselves behind the veil to protect their sovereignty. Given this context, the veil considered by various cultures as a marker of women's dignity, can also be conceived of as isolating them from their freedom of expression and aspiration. Thus, when positioning from a gender perspective, women's status in India can easily be compared to the sea and its waves in that while the waves (of oppression) constitute the sea (here referring to the society), they also need to be overcome to make progression. Time and again we may see some exceptions like Kiran Bedi, Indira Nooie, Chandra Kochar, Sonal Mansigh, and P.V.Sindhu, however, they makeup for only a handful of women to have reached an acme in their chosen career. Their presence hence cannot overshadow the dismal position of women in India who constitute around fifty percent of the population. In this regard, academicians, scholars, and researchers operating within the gender paradigm appear to come to a consensus about socialization as a factor shaping the fate of Indian women in major way (Chowdhury & Patnaik, 2013). Since human behaviour is largely channelized through gender socialisation that encompasses psychological, social and cultural inputs (Haloi, 2016), this paper seeks to outline its role in shaping the academic and career choices of women. The need for conducting a review is hence mandated to piece information together to form a coherent picture that contributes to a greater understanding of what it means to be empowered as woman.

The Women of Today: An Analysis of the Position of Women in a Contemporary India

There have been more dramatic changes in the world in the last few decades than in the past. The revolution in the telecommunication and globalisation has turned the world upside down, and a New World order is indeed emerging. We see that women have larger and more important roles than they ever did.

After sieving through the information, it is concluded that women from every walk of life are shaping social, political and economic trends. By telling their stories, by describing the trends they are shaping, by showing how they are challenging the most gender biased institutions from the medical establishments to organized religion, by offering example after example of women activists, entrepreneurs, politicians, CEO's and athletes, a case is made that the time for women to realize their potential and set their creativity free has at long last arrived. Since Independence, government of India has declared many schemes 'Sakshar Bharat Mission for Female Literacy', 'SABLA- Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls', Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, 'Beti- Bachao-Beti Padhao' to name a few. Despite these efforts of the government the challenges face by women and their access to intellectual riches can be traced to social and cultural hurdles to girls' education. The differential socio-economic status, regional variations in the availability of education are some of the reasons traced by Ramachandran (2004).

As the notion of academic equality continues to evolve, Wood (1987) argues that the concept of equal opportunities must hence underpin (a) equal life chances, (b), open competition for scarce resources (here implying the technical and professional

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